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CONTENTS

THE THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF APPLYING TAX INCENTIVES FOR INVESTMENTS DIRECTED TOWARD HUMAN CAPITAL	14
Quliyev Begimqul Melikovich	
ECONOMETRIC MODELS OF CASHLESS SETTLEMENTS AMONG ECONOMIC ENTITIES.....	21
Ruzimuradov Shukhrat Khusanovich	
PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM BRAND MARKETING IN MODERN CONDITIONS (UAE: DUBAI ON THE EXAMPLE OF A CITY).....	26
Ibodova Dilsora Ibodovna	
CREDIT DEFAULT SWAPS AS A WAY TO HEDGE AGAINST FORTHCOMING FUTURE UNCERTAINTIES IN THE DEBT MARKET OF UZBEKISTAN	31
Abduganiev Abdulaziz Alisher o'g'li	
SHOULD THE REGULATION OF THE E-COMMERCE MARKET IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN BE CARRIED OUT BY THE NATIONAL AGENCY FOR PERSPECTIVE PROJECTS OR THE CENTRAL BANK?	39
Sadikov Aziz Mirsharapovich	
MECHANISM FOR IMPLEMENTING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE OPERATIONS OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	46
Bakhriddin Berdiyarov	
INNOVATIVE APPROACHES OF SMALL BUSINESSES IN THE INDUSTRY AND CONSTRUCTION SECTORS AND THEIR IMPACT ON EMPLOYMENT.....	53
Ergasheva Nigora Abdigapparovna	
AI-BASED NORMALIZATION METHODOLOGY FOR COLLECTING AND PROCESSING KPI INDICATORS.....	56
Shuhratov Mamurjon Shuhrat o'g'li	
REFORMS AND PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PARTICIPATORY BUDGETING INITIATIVE IN UZBEKISTAN	63
Khamidov Khabibullo Hikmatulla ugli	
PROBLEMS OF THE INWARD PROCESSING CUSTOMS REGIME AND WAYS TO ELIMINATE THEM.....	70
Abdullaev Shakhzodbek	
FINANCIAL ANALYSIS OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN CONSTRUCTION	74
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
MEASURES TO ENHANCE THE ROLE AND EFFECTIVENESS OF SMALL BUSINESS IN REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT.....	80
Ergashev Jamshid Jamoliddinovich	
THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR IMPLEMENTING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION.....	84
Alijonova Marjonabonu Jaxongir qizi	
INDIA'S EXPERIENCE IN ENHANCING PUBLIC WELFARE THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY	88
Aripov Oybek Abdullayevich	
GREEN STRUCTURAL TRANSFORMATION IN UZBEKISTAN: GREEN FINANCE AND ECO-INNOVATION FOR SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIAL AND AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT.....	93
Egamberdiev Khumoyun	
AGRICULTURAL MANAGEMENT BASED ON INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES AT THE INTERNATIONAL LEVEL: THE EXAMPLE OF UZBEKISTAN.....	101
Bustonov Komiljon Kumakovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE FINANCIAL CONDITION OF ENTERPRISES: ASSESSMENT OF EQUITY EFFICIENCY	110
Umurkul Shukhratovich Fayziev	

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF ECONOMIC GROWTH THROUGH THE TRANSITION TO THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	118
Mamadaliyev Akmaljon	
МЕТОДЫ И МЕХАНИЗМЫ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ПОТРЕБИТЕЛЬСКОГО ПОВЕДЕНИЯ НА ТУРИСТСКОМ РЫНКЕ.....	124
Нурматова Ситора Шавкатовна	
ANALYSIS OF INNOVATION ACTIVITIES.....	133
Alieva Elnara Ametovna	
METHODS AND MECHANISMS FOR STUDYING CONSUMER BEHAVIOR IN THE TOURISM MARKET.....	139
Nurmatova Sitora Shavkatovna	
ALGORITHMS AND METHODS FOR CALCULATING THE AREA OF A GASTRIC ULCER DEFECT USING MODERN MATHEMATICAL TECHNIQUES.....	145
Yusupov Ibrohimbek XXX, Abdusamatova Munira Sultonbek qizi	
UTILIZATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN ENTERPRISE MARKETING ACTIVITIES.....	151
Sadikov Shohrux Shukhratovich	
ENSURING THE FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS, GLOBAL TRENDS, AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS.....	156
Inomiddin Imomov	
THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE STRUCTURE OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY.....	161
Bustonov Mansurjon Mardonakulovich	
IMPORTANT CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF E-COMMERCE SERVICES.....	169
Jurakulov Shohruh Bahtiyorovich	
AGRICULTURE PROMOTION AND DEVELOPMENT IN MOUNTAIN AND MOUNTAIN REGIONS.....	173
Abdulxayeva Gulshan Maxmudovna	
IMPROVING MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY IN SERVICE ENTERPRISES.....	178
Seytimbetov Kabul Serimbetovich	
INTEGRATION OF INTELLIGENT CONTROL IN DRYING SYSTEMS: PROCESS OPTIMIZATION THROUGH SENSORS, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, AND MODULAR DRYING.....	184
Yangiboyeva Raxbaroy Mashrabboy qizi	
THEORETICAL MODELS AND CONCEPTS OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN THE ENERGY SECTOR.....	190
Nigmatullaeva Gulchekhra Nurullaevna	
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC POTENTIAL (A CASE STUDY OF NAMANGAN REGION).....	196
Tursinbayev Azizbek Nabijon o'g'li, Sirojiddinov Kamoliddin Ikromiddinovich	
DIRECTIONS FOR DEVELOPING INVESTMENT AND EXPORT IN REMOTE SERVICE ENTERPRISES.....	203
Uzakov Ortik Shaymardanovich	
SPECIFIC FEATURES OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INCREASING THE INCOME OF THE POPULATION IN THE REGION.....	207
Kuldasheva Maftuna Musurmon kizi	
KEY FACTORS OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENT THROUGH SUBSIDIES AND INVESTMENTS TO INCREASE AGRICULTURAL CROP PRODUCTION IN UZBEKISTAN.....	211
Mamatkulova Nadira Makkamovna	
RAQAMLI MARKETING VA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA EKOTIZIM SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH USULLARI.....	216
Sobirov Azizbek Avazbekovich	
WAYS TO IMPROVE THE STATISTICAL ASSESSMENT OF FRUIT AND VEGETABLE PRODUCTION PROCESSES AND EXPORT POTENTIAL IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....	223
Anorboeva Bakhtijamol Daniyar kizi	

THE IMPACT OF DEGRADATION ON THE OPERATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PHOTOVOLTAIC MODULES UNDER SHARPLY CONTINENTAL CLIMATIC CONDITIONS	229
Qurbanov Yunus Murtaza o'g'li	
INTEGRATED NEW MEDIA OPERATION MODEL FOR INTELLIGENT TALENT ASSESSMENT PLATFORMS: THE PATH OF QR CODE ACTIVATION AND CONTENT-DRIVEN ENGAGEMENT.....	235
Wang Biao	
METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR SHAPING THE CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF YOUNGER PUPILS IN SOLVING MATHEMATICAL PROBLEMS	239
Dzhurakulova Adolat Khalmuratovna	
SOLIDWORKS-BASED MODELING OF AN AIR-BLOWING SYSTEM TO ENSURE HIGH-QUALITY FIBER REMOVAL FROM SAW TEETH	247
Mirzakarimov Mirsharoffiddin Mirzaabdurahimovich	
THEORETICAL STUDY OF TEMPERATURE AND THERMAL PHENOMENA IN MECHANICAL CUTTING OF WHITE CAST IRON.....	256
Allanazarov Akmal Abdulxaqovich	
THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGIONAL ECONOMY	262
Turdiyev Ulug'bek Qayumovich	
THE INTERRELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MIGRATION AND THE INDUSTRIAL ECONOMY	266
Khusanbek Begmatov	
THE IMPACT OF ESG PRINCIPLES ON THE HOTEL INDUSTRY	271
Khusenova Mekhrangiz	
CURRENT STATUS OF INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTION AND SERVICES MARKET IN KASHKADARYA REGION.....	276
Norov Murodjon Makhmudovich	
DEVELOPMENT OF AN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE-BASED CYBERSECURITY SYSTEM FOR THE AUTOMATIC DETECTION OF FAKE FINANCIAL RECEIPTS, PHISHING URLS, AND MALICIOUS APK FILES	284
Shermatov Axlidin Sharobiddin o'g'li	
WAYS TO INCREASE REVENUES IN COMMERCIAL BANK OPERATIONS	287
Ostonaqulova Gulchehraxon Muhammadyoqub qizi	
РОЛЬ СВОБОДНЫХ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ ЗОН В РЕГИОНАЛЬНОМ РАЗВИТИИ И ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ	301
Файзиева Ширин Шодмоновна	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH SHAROITIDA IQTISODIY O'SISH OMILLARINING TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASI.....	307
Bustonov Mansurjon Mardonakulovich	
FINTECH TRENDS: NEW TOOLS FOR ATTRACTING FINANCING IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	313
Madjitova Lolakhon Lazizovna	
CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF E-COMMERCE IN UZBEKISTAN.....	317
Toshpulatov Akhror Tukhtamurod ugli	
STRATEGIC DETERMINANTS OF FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	326
Rustamov Foziljon	
TYPES AND MEANS OF ADVERTISING IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM	335
Bahriyeva Zarina Nasimovna	
INTELLECTUALIZATION OF TECHNICAL MEANS FOR CONTROLLING TECHNOLOGICAL REFINING PROCESSES.....	340
Ruziyev Umidjon Abdimajitovich	
NECESSITY OF ENSURING AND INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF PLACEMENT MEANS	349
Sherkulov Dilshod Jurakulovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA MOLIYAVIY INKLYUZIYANING O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIK NAZARIYALARI.....	354
Adashaliyev Baxtiyorjon Valisher o'g'li	

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE AUDIT OF LEASING OPERATIONS ON FARMS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	359
Tursunov Ulugbek Sativoldievich	
METHODOLOGY DEVELOPMENT RETAIL MARKETING AND TRADING SYSTEM.....	365
Makhmatkulov Golibjon Kholmuminovich	
NECESSITY OF ENSURING AND INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF PLACEMENT MEANS	369
Sherkulov Dilshod Jurakulovich	
ENVIRONMENTAL FISCAL POLICY AS A DRIVER OF GREEN GROWTH AND EMPLOYMENT IN CENTRAL ASIA: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE	374
Rakhmatova Zilola Yurevna	
ON THE ISSUE OF CALCULATING THE POWER REQUIRED TO HEAT THE EDGES OF THE PIPE BILLET TO THE WELDING TEMPERATURE.....	379
Zairkulov Elyor Yoqubjon o'g'li	
STATISTICAL ASSESSMENT OF REGIONAL ELECTRICITY GENERATION VOLUMES.....	385
Doliev Shokhabbos Kulmurat ugli	
ANALYSIS OF ICT APPLICATION IN UZBEKISTAN'S TOURISM BASED ON EMPIRICAL RESEARCH.....	389
Nazarov Khusanbek Avazbek ogli	
METHODOLOGY FOR FORECASTING AND ANALYZING MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING INDICATORS AT AN ENTERPRISE.....	395
Minutdinova Liliya Tagirovna	
WELLNESS TOURISM AS AN ESSENTIAL COMPONENT OF HEALTH TOURISM.....	402
Tashtayeva Saida Kahharovna	
THE EXPERIENCE OF GERMANY IN DEVELOPING SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES.....	409
Annaklichev Saxi Saparmuxamedovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE APPLICATION OF THE INTERNATIONAL STANDARD ON AUDITING "ANALYTICAL PROCEDURES" IN NATIONAL AUDIT ACTIVITIES	416
Tajekeev Ziyatdin Kobeyzinovich	
ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF GREEN ENTERPRISE DEVELOPMENT IN ENSURING REGIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL SAFETY	421
Khamidillo Odilov	
A REALIST-POSITIVIST FRAMEWORK FOR ANALYSING MERGERS AND ACQUISITIONS UNDER ECONOMIC POLICY UNCERTAINTY	429
Zakhidov Azizbek Rustamovich	
DEVELOPING MATHEMATICAL MODELS TO SIMULATE THE DYNAMIC BEHAVIOR OF SEPARATION PROCESSES, CONSIDERING THE IMPACT OF EXTERNAL FACTORS	436
Abdulleva Kamola Rustamovna	
THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IMPLEMENTING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TRANSFORMATION OF BANKS.....	445
Umarova Malika Baxtiyarovna	
ON THE ISSUE OF RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT OF A SLAG-FORMING BASE FOR ELECTRODE COATINGS FOR WEAR-RESISTANT SURFACING.....	451
Sadikov Jaxongir Nasidjanovich	
MODELING OF HEAT FLOWS IN GAS-FIRED CHAMBER FURNACES.....	456
Rajabov Azamat Toirovich	
DEVELOPMENT OF A MIMO MODEL OF AZEOTROPIC DISTILLATION	462
Shamsutdinova Vinera Khafizovna	
THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE INTERACTION OF A COTTON TUFT WITH A SCREW CONVEYOR AND A MESH SURFACE.....	468
Matyaqubova Jumagul Bakhtiyarovna	
FORECASTING LIQUIDITY AND SOLVENCY INDICATORS BASED ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE	473
Zaynutdinov Ismoil Samariddin o'g'li	
MODELS FOR PREDICTING THE MANAGEMENT OF COMPLEX TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES AND PRODUCTIONS	477
Gulyamov Shukhrat Mannapovich	

WAYS TO ADJUST LAND RESOURCE USE MECHANISMS FOR FARMERS BASED ON THE EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES.....	482
Akhmatov Abutolibkhon Ochilkhon oglu	
STATE SUPPORT MECHANISMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MACHINE-BUILDING INDUSTRY	487
Xursandov Komiljon Makhmatkulovich	
EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF TOURISM FLOW FORECASTING IN CENTRAL ASIA BASED REGRESSION MODELS	491
Suratova Mokhirakhon Shavkat Kizi	
THE ROLE OF LOANS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGIONAL ECONOMY.....	498
Meylikov Fazliddin Abduhalim o'g'li, Valiev Oybek Shukhrat ugli	
PROPAGATION OF SMALL MOTIONS IN A TWO-LAYER DISPERSE MEDIA FLOW.....	503
D. S. Yakhshibaev	
FURTHER IMPROVEMENT OF THE AUTOMATION SYSTEM OF ELECTRONIC SERVICES AND TOURIST PERMITS.....	511
Najmiddinov Sultan Nurali ugli	
THE NECESSITY OF DISCLOSING INFORMATION ON SELLING EXPENSES IN ACCOUNTING REPORTS OF PHARMACEUTICAL ENTERPRISES.....	516
Xudaynazarova Dilnoza Gafurovna	
INVESTMENT FINANCIAL MECHANISMS AND THEIR ROLE IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY	521
Karjavova Khurshida Abdumalikovna	
WESTERN COUNTRIES' EXPERIENCES IN ENSURING THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF BANKING ACTIVITIES.....	526
Alimjanova Dilrabo Sobirjanovna	
MAIN FEATURES OF DIVIDEND POLICY IN COMMERCIAL BANKS.....	530
Aliyev G'ulomnozir Maxamatjonovich	
OPTIMIZATION OF THE DESIGN OF AN ENERGY- AND RESOURCE-EFFICIENT PRESSING DEVICE FOR CONVERTING DRIED LEAVES, FALLEN FOLIAGE, AND PLANT RESIDUES INTO LOCALLY PRODUCED ORGANIC FERTILIZERS.....	536
Toirova Nuriya Abdiyevna, Toirov Murtoza Shavkidinovich, Urinova Xulkar Shokirovna	
FUNDAMENTALS OF FORMING ACCOUNTING POLICIES FOR LEASING COMPANIES BASED ON INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL REPORTING STANDARDS	540
Baxadirov Alisher Komilovich	
THE USE OF DUE DILIGENCE PROCEDURES TO ENSURE TRANSPARENCY OF FINANCIAL REPORTING IN JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES	545
Prokudina Kristina Aleksandrovna	
INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE: EXAMPLES OF HISTORICAL CITIES (FLORENCE, LVIV, GRANADA, AND OTHERS)	550
Radjabova Mavluda Ergash qizi	
APPLYING LINEAR PROGRAMMING TO ANALYZE THE STATE OF COMMODITY AND RAW MATERIAL RESOURCES IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES	554
Beknazarov Farxod Abduvaxidovich, Usmanov Shakhzod Shokhrukhovich	
INTEGRATED EDUCATION MODEL IN TEACHING WATER-SAVING IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGIES.....	561
Shokhimardanova Niginabonu Shavkatovna	
IMPACT OF INFLATIONARY PROCESSES ON PROBLEM LOANS.....	566
Tojiyev Sardor Dilmurod ugli	
DIRECTIONS FOR ORGANIZING EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT IN GRAIN PRODUCT ENTERPRISES.....	572
Kurbanova Dildora Abduraxmanovna	
THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY AS A BACKBONE SECTOR OF UZBEKISTAN'S ECONOMY	576
Salomova Sarvinoz Salimovna	
BEHIND THE BENCH: THE CURRENT SITUATION OF PURCHASING LABORATORY EQUIPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	581
Kabashev Tairjon	

ISSUES OF IMPROVING AGRICULTURAL INSURANCE IN UZBEKISTAN	586
Shennayev Xo'jayor Musurmanovich	
THE LENDING SYSTEM IN COMMERCIAL BANKS AND THE CAUSES OF NON-PERFORMING LOANS	590
Shokhista K. Kholiyorova, Marjona O. Barnoqulova	
INNOVATIVE FINANCIAL INSTRUMENTS FOR FINANCING RENEWABLE ENERGY AND GREEN PROJECTS: CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATIONS	595
F. Nishonov	
DATA TRANSMISSION CONFIDENTIALITY CHALLENGES IN THE INTERNET OF THINGS.....	604
Mardiyev Ulugbek	
CURRENT ISSUES IN ADAPTING THE ACCOUNTING SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN TO INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL REPORTING STANDARDS	612
Xudoyberdiyev Odiljon Egamberdi o'g'li	
COST ANALYSIS IN FRUIT AND VEGETABLE PROCESSING PLANTS.....	618
Rahmatullayev Mirjalol Khatam ogli	
ANALYSIS OF EXPERIENCE IN ORGANIZING AND OPERATING STUDENT INNOVATION DEVELOPMENT CENTERS IN DEVELOPED COUNTRIES	624
Mirzaliev Sanjar Makhamatjan ogli	

ANALYSIS OF EXPERIENCE IN ORGANIZING AND OPERATING STUDENT INNOVATION DEVELOPMENT CENTERS IN DEVELOPED COUNTRIES

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Abstract: In the context of the modern economy, innovation and knowledge-based development have become key priorities. This article analyzes the experience of developed countries in establishing student innovation development centers and examines their operational mechanisms. The study highlights the role of these centers in supporting startups, facilitating technology transfer, attracting investment, and fostering student entrepreneurship. It also evaluates the impact of management practices, infrastructure, and collaboration on their effectiveness. Based on the findings, recommendations are proposed for improving the development of innovation centers within the national higher education system.

Key words: innovation centers, higher education, student entrepreneurship, startups, technology transfer, innovation management.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of globalization and the digital economy, innovations are increasingly becoming one of the main drivers of economic growth. Especially in a period when a knowledge-based economy is taking shape, higher education institutions must transform not only into providers of education but also into centers for the creation and commercialization of innovations. From this perspective, the establishment of student innovation development centers and ensuring their effective functioning has become a matter of particular importance in developed countries.

In recent years, studies conducted by international organizations such as the OECD and the World Economic Forum have demonstrated that innovation centers serve as important platforms for fostering creative thinking among youth, supporting startup initiatives, and transforming scientific ideas into practical outcomes. Through these centers, students not only strengthen their theoretical knowledge but also gain opportunities to adapt to real business environments, develop entrepreneurial skills, and implement innovative projects.

The relevance of this topic lies in the fact that the experience of developed countries shows that innovation development centers established within universities play a crucial role in enhancing the competitiveness of national economies. In particular, in countries such as the United States, United Kingdom, Germany, and South Korea, such centers contribute significantly to strengthening university–industry collaboration, commercializing research results, and creating high-tech products. Studying these experiences and adapting them to national conditions is an urgent scientific and practical task, especially for developing economies such as Uzbekistan.

The main objective of this scientific article is to analyze the experience of organizing student innovation development centers in developed countries, examine their operational mechanisms, and identify opportunities for applying these practices in local conditions. The research findings will contribute to the development of innovative infrastructure in higher education, support student startups, and increase innovation activity in the economy.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The issue of establishing innovation development centers within higher education systems and supporting student entrepreneurship in developed countries has been widely covered in the academic literature. Studies conducted by the OECD emphasize that higher education institutions occupy a central position in fostering innovation activity, particularly highlighting the importance of supporting student startups through the establishment of incubation centers, accelerators, and technoparks within universities. In this process, cooperation among the state, business, and educational institutions is regarded as a key factor in shaping an innovation ecosystem [1].

In her work *The Entrepreneurial State*, Mariana Mazzucato substantiates the active role of the state in innovation processes and demonstrates that government initiatives and financial support mechanisms are crucial for the development of innovation. In her view, the success of innovation centers is directly linked to the institutional environment and support system created by the state [2]. At the same time, Mitchell D. Smith emphasizes that, in the context of the modern digital economy, universities must be transformed into centers for the creation and dissemination of innovation, which in turn creates new opportunities for the development of student innovation activity [3].

In the studies of David B. Audretsch, the close relationship between entrepreneurship and economic growth is substantiated, showing that universities play an important role in creating new business entities through innovation activity. From his point of view, startups created through innovation centers become one of the main drivers of economic development [4]. Likewise, in the studies conducted by Rashid Ullah, R. Aftab, and S. Siyal, an entrepreneurship-oriented higher education system is evaluated as an effective mechanism for transforming knowledge into economic value [5].

Under the conditions of modern technological development, the issue of innovative transformation in higher education is also reflected in the works of B. Xing and Tshilidzi Marwala, who argue that, in the era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, the education system should be oriented toward the formation of new competencies [6]. At the same time, in the studies of Y. Xie, X. Liu, and Q. Yuan, the development of student innovation and entrepreneurial activity is assessed as an important factor in improving the quality of education [7].

Special attention has also been paid to this issue in studies conducted by local scholars. In particular, Saidova Xilolaxon analyzes the impact of innovation management on the quality of higher education and emphasizes that innovative management approaches are important for improving educational effectiveness [8]. Pulatova D. examines ways to increase the effectiveness of innovation management strategies and argues that a systematic approach is necessary for the development of innovation activity in the higher education system [9]. In the studies of Karimova B.X., management culture and the development of creativity are presented as important elements of pedagogical management, while the significance of human capital in the activities of innovation centers is particularly emphasized [10].

Overall, the analyzed literature shows that student innovation development centers are an important institutional element of the higher education system, and their effective functioning depends on the harmony of state policy, university governance, and business cooperation. At the same time, innovation management, digital transformation, and the development of entrepreneurial competencies emerge as the main factors for increasing the effectiveness of these centers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, the data were primarily formed on the basis of secondary sources, including academic articles, international reports, and statistical data on innovation centers operating within the higher education systems of developed countries. In particular, the databases of the OECD and the World Economic Forum were used. During the data collection process, content analysis and comparative analysis methods were applied. At the analysis stage, based on a systematic approach, the organizational structures, areas of activity, and performance indicators of innovation centers were compared with one another. In addition, logical generalization and inductive reasoning methods were used to summarize the experience of developed countries. In order to analyze the results more deeply, qualitative and quantitative analysis methods were integrated, which contributed to ensuring the reliability of the obtained findings.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis of the establishment and functioning of student innovation development centers in developed countries shows that these centers have evolved into key institutions that ensure the integration of knowledge, technology, and entrepreneurship in the modern economy. Innovation centers have moved beyond the traditional educational function of universities and have become primary platforms for commercializing research results, developing startup ecosystems, and engaging students in practical activities.

In the experience of developed countries, the establishment of innovation centers is primarily based on a triple-helix model of cooperation between universities, industry, and the state. Within this model, universities provide scientific knowledge and human capital, the business sector contributes financial resources and market mechanisms, while the state ensures a regulatory framework and institutional support. This approach increases the sustainability of innovation activities and enables effective risk-sharing.

The main areas of activity of student innovation centers can be grouped as follows:

1. Startup support and incubation. In this direction, centers facilitate the development of students' ideas from the initial stage. During the incubation process, opportunities are provided for mentorship, business plan development, marketing strategy design, and establishing connections with investors. In the experience of the United States and Europe, hundreds of successful startups have emerged through university incubators.

2. Technology transfer and commercialization. Innovation centers act as intermediaries in the implementation of research results into practice. Processes such as patenting, licensing, and transferring technologies to businesses are carried out through these centers, enabling the transformation of scientific developments into economic value.

3. Development of student entrepreneurship. Within these centers, training sessions, seminars, and practical projects are organized for students. As a result, students acquire skills in risk assessment, market analysis, and innovative thinking.

4. Attraction of investments. In developed countries, innovation centers collaborate with venture capital funds, business angels, and large companies, ensuring the financial sustainability of startups (Table 1).

Table 1. Main areas of activity of student innovation development centers in developed countries and their content

Area of activity	Description	Key tools	Expected outcomes
Startup incubation	Process of transforming students' ideas into business projects	Incubators, mentorship programs, business plan development	Creation of new startups, development of entrepreneurial skills
Technology transfer	Commercialization of research results	Patenting, licensing, technology transfer offices	Creation of innovative products, application of research in practice
Development of student entrepreneurship	Formation of business and innovative thinking among students	Trainings, seminars, acceleration programs	Growth of entrepreneurial competencies
Investment attraction	Expansion of funding sources for startups	Venture funds, business angels, grants	Financial sustainability, rapid project growth
Collaboration and networking	Development of university–industry–government relations	Partnership platforms, forums, joint projects	Strengthening of the innovation ecosystem

The analysis of this table shows that in developed countries, student innovation development centers operate as complex and multifunctional systems. Their main advantage lies not in specialization in a single area, but in covering the entire innovation chain—from startup creation to financing and commercialization. In particular, investment attraction and technology transfer play a crucial role in increasing the economic efficiency of innovation activities. At the same time, the development of student entrepreneurship improves the quality of human capital. As a result, innovation centers become not only a component of the education system but also an important driver of economic development.

The above-mentioned areas of activity demonstrate that innovation centers function as integrated systems. Their effectiveness largely depends on the management model and the level of resource provision.

In developed countries, the management mechanisms of innovation centers have their own distinctive features. Analysis shows that the following factors determine their success:

First, the presence of strategic management. Innovation centers possess long-term development strategies aligned with the overall strategy of the university, ensuring consistency in their activities.

Second, professional management. In developed countries, specialists with business experience are involved in managing innovation centers, which enables more effective organization of their operations.

Third, financial diversification. Innovation centers do not rely solely on public funding but expand their revenue sources through grants, private investments, and service-based income.

Fourth, infrastructure development. Modern laboratories, coworking spaces, and technoparks create the necessary conditions for innovation activities (Table 2).

Table 2. Management mechanisms and efficiency factors of student innovation development centers in developed countries

Factors	Description	Implementation tools	Impact
Strategic management	Defining long-term development directions	Strategic plans, KPI systems, monitoring mechanisms	Ensures sustainability and goal-oriented activity
Professional management	Involvement of experienced management personnel	Business-experienced managers, experts	Improves decision quality and operational efficiency
Financial diversification	Use of multiple funding sources	Grants, venture capital, government subsidies, private investments	Enhances financial stability and reduces risks
Innovation infrastructure	Modern technological and working environment	Technoparks, laboratories, coworking spaces	Accelerates innovation activity
Collaboration networks	Integration of university–industry–government	Clusters, consortiums, international partnerships	Strengthens knowledge exchange and resource flows
Digital technologies	Digitalization of innovation processes	Online platforms, AI tools, big data analytics	Increases speed and efficiency

The analysis of this table shows that the effectiveness of student innovation development centers in developed countries is not accidental but rather the result of a systematic process based on well-defined management mechanisms. Several key aspects stand out in this process:

1. Priority of a strategic approach. Innovation centers are oriented toward long-term development goals rather than short-term results, which ensures their sustainability.
2. Decisive role of human capital. The presence of professional management improves governance quality and supports the effective implementation of innovative projects.
3. Ensuring financial stability through diversification. Funding from multiple sources makes innovation centers more resilient to external shocks.
4. High level of infrastructure and technological support. Modern technoparks and laboratories provide the necessary environment for innovation activities.
5. Broad collaboration networks. Links between universities, businesses, and the state strengthen the innovation ecosystem.
6. Role of digitalization. Digital technologies accelerate innovation processes and significantly increase efficiency.

Overall, the integration of these factors ensures the high performance of innovation centers and transforms them into important institutional elements of the modern economy.

A number of indicators are used to evaluate the effectiveness of innovation centers. Among them, particular importance is given to the number of startups, the volume of attracted investments, the number of jobs created, and the number of commercialized technologies. At the same time, the level of development of students' competencies is also considered an important indicator.

A deeper analysis of the experience of developed countries also reveals regional and institutional differences. For example, in the United States, innovation centers are more market-driven, whereas in European countries, state support is more prominent. In countries such as South Korea and Singapore, innovation centers operate in close alignment with national strategies.

In addition, the success of innovation centers largely depends on human capital. Effective collaboration among students, faculty, and entrepreneurs enables the rapid development of innovative ideas. Therefore, in developed countries, practical components are widely integrated into the educational process, including project-based learning and interactive teaching methods.

The analysis also shows that digital technologies play a crucial role in the activities of innovation centers. Online platforms, artificial intelligence-based analytical tools, and digital ecosystems accelerate innovation processes and increase efficiency. Particularly in the post-pandemic period, the importance of remote collaboration and virtual incubation models has significantly increased.

At the same time, certain challenges remain. For instance, not all students are equally engaged in innovation activities, and access to financial resources is sometimes limited. However, the experience of developed countries demonstrates that these challenges can be addressed through institutional reforms and improvements in innovation policy.

Overall, student innovation development centers are emerging as key mechanisms for transforming knowledge into economic value in the modern economy. Through in-depth study of their activities and adaptation

of advanced practices to local conditions, it is possible to foster an innovative environment in higher education, promote youth entrepreneurship, and accelerate economic growth.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, in developed countries, student innovation development centers have become an integral part of the higher education system and a key driver of the innovation economy. Through these centers, scientific knowledge is translated into practice, student startup initiatives are supported, and effective university–industry–government collaboration is established. The analysis shows that the success of such centers primarily depends on strategic management, financial diversification, developed infrastructure, and strong collaboration networks. At the same time, innovation centers play an important role in developing entrepreneurial skills among youth, creating new jobs, and accelerating economic growth.

In order to further develop this area, it is appropriate to propose the following recommendations:

1. To establish innovation development centers within higher education institutions and develop them based on a unified national strategy.
2. To improve mechanisms for the commercialization of innovative projects by strengthening university–industry–government collaboration.
3. To develop venture funds, grant programs, and business angel institutions to finance student startups.
4. To expand innovation infrastructure, particularly by developing networks of technoparks, incubators, and accelerators.
5. To promote student entrepreneurship by widely integrating practical and project-based approaches into the educational process.
6. To introduce systems for managing innovation activities based on digital technologies and artificial intelligence.
7. To develop a clear system of performance indicators for evaluating innovation centers and improve monitoring mechanisms.

Overall, by thoroughly studying the experience of developed countries and adapting it to national conditions, it is possible to effectively organize student innovation development centers, create an innovative environment within the higher education system, and ensure sustainable economic development.

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